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EFFECT OF EXTREME CLIMATE ON HUMAN PHYSIOLOGICAL DISCOMFORT IN JOS METROPOLIS, PLATEAU STATE

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ABSTRACT

Amid rising global climate concerns, Jos Metropolis in Nigeria, a high-altitude city historically known for temperate conditions, now experiences abrupt temperature fluctuations (“Jos weather”) that induce significant physiological discomfort. This study investigated (i) specific weather conditions causing discomfort, (ii) the nature and extent of discomfort during extreme heat/cold, (iii) the most affected demographic groups, and (iv) coping strategy effectiveness. A descriptive survey design was adopted targeting 1,101,300 residents of Jos North and South LGAs (NPC, 2022). Using Taro Yamane’s formula, 400 respondents were selected via stratified random sampling. A validated questionnaire (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.818$) and Landsat-derived LST analysis (2014–2024) were employed. Results revealed extreme heat and cold spells as primary drivers, causing respiratory issues, dehydration, and joint pain, worsened by urban expansion (+7.474 km² built-up area). The elderly are most vulnerable, with significant demographic differences (ANOVA $F(3,379) = 6.247$, $p = 0.001$) and a strong climate-discomfort relationship ($r = 0.672$, $p < 0.001$). Current coping strategies offer only moderate relief. The study recommends portable fans, insulated clothing, cooling centres, N95 mask distribution, GIS-based vulnerability mapping, and aggressive green infrastructure development to mitigate escalating health risks in Jos Metropolis.

Keywords: Extreme climate, physiological discomfort, Jos Metropolis, urban heat island, social vulnerability

INTRODUCTION

Across the globe, extreme climatic conditions have become more frequent, prolonged, and severe, directly threatening human physiological comfort and health (Molla, 2025; Baecker, Iyengar, Del Piccolo, & Mechelli, 2025). In Europe, the 2003 and 2022 heatwaves claimed tens of thousands of lives, predominantly among the elderly and outdoor workers, while triggering surges in cardiovascular and respiratory related issues (Linares, Díaz, Negev, Martínez, Debono, & Paz, 2020). Asia, particularly China, has recorded escalating heat-related mortality, cognitive impairment, reduced labour productivity, and cardiovascular events even at moderate temperature elevations of 25–30 °C (Tian, Zhu, Zheng, & Wei, 2011; Wu, Li, & Ye, 2025). Nigeria, Africa’s most

populous nation, mirrors and magnifies these continental trends. Record temperatures exceeding 44 °C have been registered in northern cities, while urban centres like Lagos, Abuja, are increasingly face with prolonged heat spells, erratic harmattan dust episodes, and unpredictable rainfall (Adelekan, 2013; Saad-Hussein, Anwer, & Abdul, 2025). Poor ventilation, high population density, and inadequate cooling infrastructure amplify physiological stress, leading to rising incidences of heat exhaustion, dehydration, and respiratory complications (Tian, et al, 2011; Abubakar & Jin, 2023). Jos Metropolis, situated at 1,200–1,300 metres above sea level on the Jos Plateau, was long regarded as Nigeria’s climatic sanctuary. Historically mild daytime temperatures of 20–26 °C and cool nights of

7–10 °C earned it the affectionate titles “Little London” and “Nigeria’s natural air-conditioner” (Wuyep, Samuel, & Yakubu, 2015; Danbauchi, 2023). This pleasant high-altitude climate supported thriving agriculture, tin mining, tourism, and a reputation as the country’s most thermally comfortable urban centre (Wuyep & Madaki, 2020). However, recent decades have witnessed a dramatic shift: satellite-derived land surface temperature records reveal a 1.36 °C increase between 2010 and 2024, driven by rapid urbanisation, vegetation loss, and expanding built-up areas (Wuyep & Madaki, 2020; Zitta, Akinpelu, & Emmanuel, 2021). Residents now routinely experience intense midday heat exceeding 33 °C contrasted against chilly harmattan mornings below 13 °C, a phenomenon locally described as “Jos weather” (Wuyep, Damak, Daloeng, Arin, & Binbol, 2021). These abrupt intra-day temperature swings, combined with prolonged dry-season heat and dust-laden harmattan winds, place unprecedented strain on human thermoregulation, yet the resulting

physiological discomfort and adaptive responses remain largely unexamined. Despite growing global concern over extreme climate impacts on human health, this remains limited understanding of how residents of Jos Metropolis, physically experience and respond to these conditions. This study therefore investigates what specific weather conditions are most responsible for causing physical discomfort among residents in Jos Metropolis, what is the nature and extent of physical discomfort experienced by residents and which categories of people are most affected by extreme weather in Jos Metropolis?

Materials and Methods

The study area, Jos Metropolis lies 9.9285° N, 8.8921° E, 1,200–1,300 m above sea level. It has a temperature of 20–26 °C Day, 7–10 °C night Figure 1. Recent satellite records confirm a 1.36 °C rise in surface temperature and increasing diurnal swings due to urbanisation and vegetation loss (Zitta et al., 2021; Wuyep et al., 2021), making it an ideal setting to investigate emerging physiological discomfort in a rapidly changing high-altitude tropical city.

Figure 1: Plateau State, showing the Study Area

This study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design complemented by remote sensing to examine the relationship between extreme climate and physiological discomfort in Jos Metropolis. The target population comprised 1,101,300 residents of Jos North and Jos South LGAs (National Population Commission, 2022). Using Taro Yamane’s formula at 95 % confidence level and 5 % margin of error, a sample size of 400 respondents was derived. Stratified random sampling was employed: 11 political wards (6 from Jos North, 5 from Jos South) were purposively selected to represent urban and peri-urban diversity, and respondents were proportionally allocated (218 from Jos North, 182 from Jos South) across age, gender, and occupation groups.

Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire containing Likert-scale and multiple-choice items on weather conditions, discomfort symptoms, demographic characteristics, and coping strategies. The instrument achieved a Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.888. Secondary data comprised Digital Landsat 8/9 images (2019–2024) processed via Remote Sensing and GIS to generate land surface temperature (LST) maps and quantify urban heat island intensification (Wuyep & Akinseye, 2020). Data analysis utilised SPSS version 26 for descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means) and

inferential tests: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient tested H_{01} (relationship between extreme climate and discomfort), while One-Way ANOVA tested H_{02} (differences across age, gender, and occupation). GIS overlay analysis integrated geocoded questionnaire responses with LST and vegetation cover layers to produce vulnerability maps highlighting high-risk zones. These methods were chosen for their ability to combine vigorous quantitative human-centred data with objective environmental measurements, ensuring reliable, representative, and spatially explicit findings on a previously understudied phenomenon.

This study adopts a conceptual framework that posits a direct causal relationship between extreme climate (independent variable); manifested as prolonged heatwaves, cold spells, and erratic temperature swings, and human physiological discomfort (dependent variable), evidenced by dehydration, excessive sweating, shivering, fatigue, dizziness, and heat-/cold-related illnesses (Kothari, 2004). The relationship is moderated by socio-demographic factors including age, gender, occupation, housing quality, and duration of exposure, which determine differential vulnerability and intensity of discomfort experienced (Nata’ala et al., 2024) Figure 2.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework connecting the independent variables and dependent variables

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Socio-demographic Information of Respondents

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	103	26.9
	Male	280	73.1
Age	26-35 Years	105	27.4
	36-45 Years	152	39.7
	46 - 55 Years	84	21.9
	56-65 Years	28	7.3
	66 Years and Above	14	3.7
Occupation	Business	139	36.3
	Formal Employment (government and organized private sector)	117	30.5
	Other	48	12.5
	Student	72	18.8
	Unemployed	7	1.8
Residential Area	Jos North	173	45.1
	Jos South	210	54.9
Housing Type	Formal (e.g, concrete, well- ventilated, gated)	222	58.0
	Informal (e.g, mud house, temporary structures)	161	42.0
	Total	383	100.0

Table 1 reveals that respondents were predominantly male (73.1 % vs. 26.9 % female), mostly working-age (67.1 % under 45 years), and economically active (66.8 % in business or formal employment). The largest age group was 36–45 years (39.7 %). More respondents resided in Jos South (54.9 %) than Jos North (45.1 %), with 58 % in formal

housing and 42 % in informal structures. These demographics suggest higher exposure and vulnerability among outdoor workers and informal dwellers to extreme heat, cold, and dust-related discomfort (Akerlof, 2015; Wuyep, Damak, & Daloeng, Arin, Binbol, 2021).

Figure 3: Weather condition causing physical discomfort most in Jos

Figure 3 reveals that extreme heat (36.8 %) and cold spells (36.0 %) are almost equally the leading causes of physical discomfort in Jos Metropolis, far ahead of flooding (1.6 %), other conditions (22.7 %), or no effect (2.9 %). This near tie confirms that both intense midday heat and chilly harmattan nights/cold spells are the dominant climatic stressors, aligning with Wuyep et al. (2021) who

documented strong heat stress at 32–38 °C alongside significant cold exposure in Jos’s high-altitude environment, and further supported by Nasara et al. (2024) and Zitta et al. (2021) who noted the city’s transformation from a cool refuge into a zone of dual thermal extremes due to urbanisation-driven temperature rise.

Table 2: Respondents’ experience discomfort from extreme heat

Response		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	90	23.5	23.5	23.5
	Often	51	13.3	13.3	36.8
	Rarely	71	18.5	18.5	55.4
	Sometimes	171	44.6	44.6	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 indicates that the majority of respondents (44.6 %) sometimes experience physical discomfort from extreme heat, followed by 23.5 % who always do, 13.3 % often, and 18.5 % rarely. This shows extreme heat is a recurring source of discomfort for most residents, consistent with Anderson (2014), who, using wearable physiological sensors in urban Atlanta, documented

significantly elevated heart rates, skin temperatures, and reports of fatigue and heat cramps during periods of high heat, attributing these frequent heat-related discomforts directly to the amplifying influence of urban heat island effects in densely built environments; a clear pattern mirrored in Jos by rapid built-up expansion (Wuyep & Akinseye, 2020).

Table 3: Respondents' experience discomfort from extreme cold

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	171	44.6	44.6	44.6
	Often	90	23.5	23.5	68.1
	Rarely	71	18.5	18.5	86.5
	Sometimes	51	13.3	13.3	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 reveals that the majority (44.6 %) always experience discomfort from extreme cold, followed by 23.5 % often, 18.5 % rarely, and 13.3 % sometimes. This indicates extreme cold is a persistent and dominant source of physical discomfort in Jos Metropolis, strongly supporting Omonijo (2017) who documented frequent cold-related distress during harmattan spells in Nigerian urban settings, and corroborated by Beker, Cervellera, De Vito, and Musso, (2018) who explain that prolonged cold

exposure in high-altitude environments induces sustained peripheral vasoconstriction, shivering, and increased metabolic demand, often overwhelming thermoregulatory capacity. This leads to persistent hypothermia-like symptoms, joint stiffness, and cardiovascular strain even at moderate cold levels (below 15 °C). Their findings strongly corroborate the present study's result that 44.6 % of Jos residents always experience discomfort from extreme cold during harmattan spells.

Figure 4: Severity of Discomfort caused by Harmattan Dust in Jos

Figure 4 shows harmattan dust severity in Jos: 44.4 % rated it moderately severe (majority), 24.8 % slightly severe, 23.8 % very severe, and 7.0 % not severe. This confirms harmattan dust as a widespread moderate respiratory irritant, aligning with

Balogun (2016) on prevalent moderate dust-related discomfort in northern Nigeria and reinforced by Nasara, et al., (2024), who, using the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) over 1980–2020, linked harmattan dust to elevated respiratory morbidity

through increased particulate matter and low humidity exacerbating airway irritation, dry coughs, and asthma attacks, particularly in urban northern Nigeria where dust events

correlate with 20–30 % higher hospital admissions for bronchial issues during peak seasons.

Figure 5: How heavy rainfall or flooding disrupt daily activities

Figure 5 shows that heavy rainfall/flooding moderately disrupts daily activities for the majority (39.4 %), with 26.6 % unaffected, 23.5 % greatly affected, 7.0 % slightly, and 3.4 % completely disrupted. Overall, flooding causes moderate disruption among Jos residents, far less severe than extreme heat or cold spells. These results are in consistent with Okunlola (2019) and Ekpoh (2010) who observed that while flooding occurs, thermal extremes remain the primary climatic burden in northern Nigerian cities.

Weather Conditions with LST Analysis:

Results confirm extreme heat (36.8 %) and cold spells (36.0 %) as dominant discomfort drivers in Jos Metropolis, followed by harmattan dust (22.7 %) and flooding (1.6

%). Heat discomfort affects 44.6 % sometimes and 23.5 % always (Anderson, 2014); cold discomfort affects 44.6 % always (Omonijo, 2017). Harmattan dust is moderately severe for 44.4 % (Balogun, 2016; Nasara et al., 2024), while flooding moderately disrupts activities for 39.4 % (Okunlola, 2019). 2024 LST analysis reveals +7.474 km² built-up expansion, intensifying urban heat islands, with declining vegetation (-5.726 km²) and water bodies (-7.163 km²) worsening heat stress and dust retention in urban zones (Anderson, 2014; Wuyep et al., 2021; Isioye et al., 2020; Zitta et al., 2021). The 2024 LST heat map (Figure 6) provides visual evidence of these temperature disparities.

Figure 6: LST 2014 Map

Table 4: Physical discomfort experienced most during extreme weather

Response		Frequen cy	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Dehydration/Thirst	110	28.7	28.7	28.7
	Fatigue/Weakness of the body	60	15.7	15.7	44.4
	Joint Pain	75	19.6	19.6	64.0
	Other	10	2.6	2.6	66.6
	Respiratory Issues like coughing	128	33.4	33.4	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 reveals respiratory issues (coughing, 33.4 %) as the most common physical discomfort during extreme weather in Jos, followed by dehydration (28.7 %), joint pain (19.6 %), and fatigue (15.7 %). This confirms harmattan dust as a major health threat, consistent with Balogun (2016) on prevalent respiratory distress in northern Nigeria and supported by Xu, Yu, Liu, Chen, Yang, Zhang, & Guo, (2023) who found that during Australia’s dry, cold seasons, fine particulate matter from dust events significantly

aggravates airway inflammation, leading to increased coughing, wheezing, and asthma exacerbations even at moderate concentrations. They specifically noted that cold, low-humidity conditions enhance dust penetration into the lower respiratory tract, explaining why respiratory issues (33.4 %) emerged as the leading discomfort in Jos during harmattan-dominated extreme weather, mirroring the same dust–cold synergy observed in northern Nigeria.

Table 5: The extent to which extreme cold cause joint pain or discomfort

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Greatly	126	32.9	32.9	32.9
	Moderately	146	38.1	38.1	71.0
	Not at all	34	8.9	8.9	79.9
	Slightly	77	20.1	20.1	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 and related results show respiratory issues (33.4 %) and dehydration (37.9 % often affected) as the dominant discomforts in Jos, with joint pain from extreme cold moderately affecting most respondents (38.1 %). The 2014–2024 LST analysis confirms urban expansion (+7.474 km²) and vegetation/water loss intensify heat islands, worsening dehydration and dust-related

respiratory distress (Wuyep et al., 2021; Anderson, 2014; Sheng et al., 2025; Isioye et al., 2020; Zitta et al., 2021). This urban-induced environmental degradation amplifies both heat stress and harmattan dust retention, creating a compound threat that disproportionately heightens physiological burden in densely built-up areas.

Figure 7: LST 2024 Map

Figure 8: Group that is most affected by extreme weather in Jos Communities

Categories of People Affected by Extreme Weather

Figure 8 reveals the elderly (48.0 %) are most affected by extreme weather in Jos, followed by low-income households (23.8 %), outdoor workers (19.3 %), and children (8.9 %). The majority confirm the elderly as the most vulnerable group, consistent with Adger (2010), who demonstrated that older adults experience greater health declines from climate extremes owing to reduced physiological resilience, limited mobility,

and poorer access to adaptive resources. Akerlof (2015) found that individuals aged 65 and above suffer 50 % higher rates of heat-related illness because of impaired thermoregulation and higher prevalence of comorbidities; and Liang et al. (2025), who showed through large-scale longitudinal data that every 1 °C temperature deviation increases cardiovascular and respiratory risks in the elderly by 8–12 %, thereby amplifying their overall vulnerability to both heat and cold stress

Figure 9: How extreme heat affects elderly residents in Jos communities

Figure 9 shows extreme heat affects the elderly greatly (44.1 %), moderately (34.2 %), severely (14.9 %), and slightly (6.8 %). The majority confirm extreme heat impacts elderly residents most significantly, reinforcing Social Vulnerability Theory (Cutter, 2003), which argues that vulnerability is not only exposure-driven but socially constructed; pre-existing inequalities (age-related physiological decline, comorbidities, limited mobility, lower adaptive capacity) amplify harm from the

same hazard. This is corroborated by Zhou et al. (2025), who found older adults face significantly higher cardiovascular mortality and heat-stroke risk during extreme heat events.

4.3 TEST OF HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: Extreme climate has no significant effect on physiological discomfort among residents of Jos Metropolis.

Table 6: The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Pearson r	Sig. (2-tailed)
Extreme Climate	383	3.94	0.87	0.672**	0.000
Physiological Discomfort	383	3.76	0.91		

Pearson correlation ($r = 0.672$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) shows a strong, significant positive relationship between extreme climate and physiological discomfort in Jos Metropolis. Thus, H₀₁ is rejected; extreme climatic conditions significantly increase residents' discomfort. This supports Anderson (2014) who recorded measurable rises in heart rate, dehydration, and fatigue under urban heat

stress; Wuyep et al. (2021) who documented Jos' rising heat-island intensity and cold extremes and Naumann et al. (2020) who demonstrated that combined heat-cold extremes across Europe produce greater physiological burden than single stressors, confirming the compounded impact observed in Jos.

H₀₂: There is no difference in physiological discomfort across age, gender, or occupation in Jos Metropolis.

Table 7: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.483	3	4.161	6.247	0.001
Within Groups	251.398	379	0.663		
Total	263.881	382			

Source: Field Survey, 2025 (IBM SPSS v.26 Output)

ANOVA ($F(3,379) = 6.247, p = 0.001 < 0.05$) confirms significant differences in physiological discomfort across age, gender, and occupation. Outdoor workers and the elderly experience markedly higher discomfort than others. H_0 is rejected, supporting Adger (2010) who showed older age and poverty amplify climate impacts through reduced adaptive capacity; Okunlola

CONCLUSION

Extreme climate significantly affects residents of Jos Metropolis, with extreme heat and cold spells, emerging as the dominant triggers of physiological discomfort, producing widespread respiratory issues, dehydration, and joint pain (moderately to greatly affecting 71.0 % during cold spells). These dual stressors are intensified by rapid urbanisation, evidenced by a +7.474 km² built-up expansion and significant loss of vegetation and water bodies between 2014 and 2024, amplifying urban heat island effects and harmattan dust exposure. The elderly are the most vulnerable group, experiencing extreme heat followed by low-income households and outdoor workers, confirming significant demographic differences (ANOVA $p = 0.001$). A strong positive relationship exists between extreme climate and physiological discomfort ($r = 0.672, p < 0.001$), validating Social Vulnerability Theory (Cutter, 2003). Without urgent, targeted interventions, rising temperatures and persistent harmattan conditions will continue to escalate health risks and diminish quality of life in this once-temperate high-altitude city.

(2019) who found Nigerian outdoor workers suffer greater exposed to heat/flood risks; Liang et al. (2025) who reported 8–12 % higher health vulnerability per 1 °C temperature shift in elderly and manual labourers; and validating Cutter's (2003) Social Vulnerability Theory that pre-existing social inequalities systematically magnify harm from identical climatic hazards

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made:

1. Residents should adopt portable fans, insulated clothing, and increased hydration; government must establish community cooling/heating centres and install real-time meteorological stations across Jos North and South.
2. Health NGOs should distribute N95 masks and conduct aggressive public education on hydration and dust protection during harmattan.
3. Government should provide subsidised cooling devices and thermal blankets to the elderly and low-income households, while geographers use GIS to map high-risk zones for targeted relief.
4. Both residents and city authorities should prioritise tree planting and green infrastructure to combat urban heat islands and improve natural cooling.

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